

Blending Spirituality and Leadership Abilities for Sustainable Management: A Comprehensive Approach

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Abstract:

This research examines the relationship between spirituality and leadership abilities within the framework of sustainable management. Spirituality is seen as a core element that links people to one another and to a higher power or ultimate truth. Spirituality, in addition to leadership skills, enhances modern management theories and practices. The study explores how leaders might draw inspiration from spirituality to effectively fulfil their duties and responsibilities in promoting sustainability within organisations. The growing focus on sustainability following corporate scandals and worldwide economic crises highlights the importance of embracing a comprehensive approach that combines talents, spirituality, and their significance in management. The paper highlights the significance of empowered leadership and moral authority in promoting sustainable management practices, drawing on literature from social psychology and leadership. The article also explores the idea of workplace spirituality and its effects on organisational dynamics. The report contends that integrating leadership abilities with spirituality can result in more efficient and ethical leadership, promoting a culture of trust, cooperation, and organisational achievement.

Keywords: *empowered leadership, spirituality leadership, sustainable management, workplace spirituality*